

Interactive Learning Strategies and the Vocabulary Knowledge of Grade Seven Students

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ABSTRACT: Vocabulary is an essential component that one should be mastered in language learning. A robust vocabulary matters because it improves all areas of communication-listening, speaking, reading and writing. The students' vocabulary will be their tool towards achieving the concept of what they are trying to read or listen. It is a pre-requisite for grammar and language proficiency. In this study, the researcher employed the interactive learning strategies (ILS) such as the word wizard, word connect, synonyms word game and day's word in teaching English subject among sixty (60) Grade 7 students who are divided into two experimental groups to find out whether these strategies will help the students improve their vocabulary knowledge in terms of word meaning, word use and context clues. Based on the results of the study, the findings revealed that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of experimental group 1 which indicates that the use of interactive learning strategies-word wizard and word connect helped students to improve their vocabulary knowledge. Likewise, similar findings for experimental group 2 was obtained due to a significant difference between their pretest and posttest mean scores which signifies that the use of interactive learning strategies-synonyms word game and day's word, improved their vocabulary knowledge. Thus, the null hypotheses are rejected.

KEYWORDS: context clues, interactive, synonyms, word connect, word wizard

INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is an essential component that one should be mastered in language learning. The students' vocabulary is their tool towards achieving the concept of what they are trying to read. Vocabulary is a pre-requisite for grammar and language proficiency. Moreover, it is a crucial component of the four macro skills. Students should learn new words and be able to use them as tools for communication. Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. The most important point of this statement is that mastering vocabulary for the students is the main component in order to learn a language successfully. If one has prior knowledge or a word is present in his schema, then a student can easily build connections and make meaning out of what he is studying. It is believed that when someone has a wider vocabulary in the target language it also helps all four language skills such as reading, writing, listening and speaking [1].

One of the most significant aspects of language learning for the students is to have rich and efficient vocabulary. Vocabulary as the total number of words with corresponding meanings. These words serve as the fuel for the students to express themselves in a clear and concise manner whether in written or spoken format. One of the most essentials aspects of language learning is the student's vocabulary development. Moreover, vocabulary plays a very significant role in developing the macro skills [2].

The students nowadays have a very limited vocabulary knowledge in the second language which can be observed whenever they read or listen to a particular material. This may sometimes lead them to lose their focus on what they are reading or listening. Moreover, there are times when students are having trouble on how a word must be correctly spelled or how it should be used appropriately in a sentence. During the class discussion, students are expressing words using their mother tongue because they do not know the exact term of it in English. It is a proof that students have the idea however, lack of vocabulary limits them to express themselves freely using the second language. Even in writing, students always ask the teacher for the equivalent term of a particular word in English because of poor vocabulary. Thus, these observations lead the researcher to conduct the study of using the Interactive Learning Strategies (ILS) for them to develop vocabulary. The researcher's desire is to use interactive learning strategies that will provide opportunities for students to improve their vocabulary while enjoying the activities given in every lesson.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to find out the effect of Interactive Learning Strategies (ILS) such as word wizard, word connect, synonyms word game and day's word in the vocabulary knowledge of Grade 7 students in the School Year 2022-2023. The study focused on two sections in grade 7 who served as experimental group 1 and 2.

This study tested the significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group 1 of respondents before and after using the interactive learning strategies such as word wizard and word connect. In the same manner, the significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of experimental group 2 students before and after using the interactive learning strategies such as synonyms word game and day's word activity was also tested.

Moreover, the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents before and after using the pre-reading activities was also given emphasis.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design specifically the two-groups pre-test post-test design to determine whether the student-respondents' vocabulary knowledge have improved after using the Interactive Learning Strategies.

Experimental research design is doing research in a methodical, controlled manner which ensures that accuracy is maximized and that particular inferences about a hypothesis statement can be made. Normally, the goal is to determine the impact a factor, independent variable, or dependent variable has on another.

The pre-test was given to students to assess their vocabulary development before utilizing the interactive learning strategies. Post-test was given after the use of interactive learning strategies to determine if vocabulary knowledge has improved during the conduct of the study.

Respondents of the Study

The study was conducted in Atty. Celso M. Reyes Integrated National High School of Candelaria West District situated in the municipality of Candelaria, Quezon. The respondents of the study were sixty (60) randomly selected Grade 7 students who belong to different sections for the school year 2022-2023. These students came from the two heterogeneous sections of Grade 7. Thirty (30) randomly selected students were considered as the experimental group 1 who were taught using Word Wizard and Word Connect. On the other hand, the other thirty (30) randomly selected students from another section were considered as the experimental group 2 who were taught using Day's Word and Synonyms Word Game. In experimental group 1, 46.67% of the respondents are male while 53.33% of the respondents are female. On the other hand, experimental group 2 is comprised of 40% male respondents and 60% of the respondents are female. All the students who undergone the experiment were taking English subject under the researcher's English classes. Based on the researcher's observation in the class, most of the respondents are having difficulty identifying vocabulary meaning. They are also characterized for being actively engaged if the learning activities provided for them is fun and enjoyable. On the contrary, they easily get bored when they are just listening to the discussion for the whole period.

Research Instrument

To determine the effect of the various interactive learning strategies such as word wizard, word connect, synonyms word game and day's word to the vocabulary knowledge of the two groups of respondents, pre-test were prepared first then administered. An adapted modified tests for pretest and posttest in vocabulary were the three skills are specified in the test such as word meaning, word use and context clues were used. Eight (8) Lesson Exemplars which were used to implement the strategies were crafted. These cater the four (4) learning competencies of grade seven students of third quarter for the school year 2022-2023.

The first set of Lesson Exemplars were made for experimental group 1 who were exposed to Word Wizard and Word Connect. In the said exemplars, four learning competencies were targeted to be achieved. The researcher made sure that the activities are all interactive and interrelated with one another. The interactive learning strategies for experimental group 1, were specifically placed in the development part of the lesson wherein the researcher intended to capture students' interest before the discussion proper especially for lessons containing literature.

Conversely, the second set of Lesson Exemplars were crafted for the experimental group 2 who experienced Day's Word and Synonyms Word Game. The only difference is the execution of the lesson and different strategies were used. The researcher allows the students to become more independent in the day's word activity since they are given tasks to explain the meaning of the word, its translation and how to use it in a sentence. On the other hand, the synonyms word game challenged the students critical thinking skills since they have to create a good comparison between pairs of words provided by the researcher.

Research Procedure

The researcher conducted the study during the third quarter of the school year 2022-2023. The lessons were based on the MELCS provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) and teacher's IDEA Lesson Exemplar (LE). The lessons were discussed using different strategies during activities to make the students engaged individually or in groups. The four interactive strategies such as

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word wizard, word connect, synonyms word game and day's word were used during the period of the experiment, and strategies were divided into lessons/topics for the whole quarter.

The researcher made use of an adapted modified test to measure students' vocabulary knowledge. The instrument was validated first by the subject specialist. For the content and face validity, three external validators checked the said instrument. The researcher incorporated the suggestions provided by the validators. Afterwards, the researcher, with the approval of her adviser and the statistician, then conducted the pilot testing to ensure test reliability. There were twelve (12) Grade 8 students who participated in the conduct of pilot testing. The responses were tallied and subjected for item analysis. The researcher used the result of item analysis to revise or even alter some of the test questions. After the instrument was finalized, the researcher administered the pretest to the respondents as the first assessment of their vocabulary knowledge.

During the experiment, the lessons intended for that week were discussed by the researcher through interactive learning strategies to the group of respondents. The lessons indicated in Lesson Exemplars are good for four weeks having one lesson each week. For the experimental group 1, the researcher applied the word connect and word wizard strategy alternately for four lessons in English 7. The strategies were used in the introduction and development part of the Lesson exemplar (LE).

The experimental group 2 were also taught using two interactive learning strategies which are the synonyms word game and day's word alternately. These strategies can be found in the introduction and the development part of the Lesson Exemplars (LE). There were four learning competencies targeted and indicated in Lesson Exemplars which are also good for four weeks having one lesson or competency each week. The researcher utilized instructional and authentic materials which made the strategies appealing to the students like the box, the day's word corner, reward and even a ball to make the strategy gamified.

Posttest was given to the two experimental groups of respondents who have undergone the experiment after the period of lessons stated in the lesson exemplar.

After the pretest and posttest, the researcher then collected the data, and submitted to the statistician for the treatment. It was then tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

For ethical considerations, the researcher sought the permission from the Division Office Superintendent, District Supervisor and the head of the school to conduct the study and submit letter of consent to utilize the chosen students who will serve as the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After the gathering of the data, these were subjected for statistical treatment. The researcher tabulated the raw data. Then it was submitted to statistics center for the statistical tools to be used for better analysis and discussions. The researcher then, analyzed and interpreted the results.

Aside from the mean scores, to get the significant difference of the pretest and posttest between the two experimental groups of respondents, Test of difference was used. T-test for dependent and independent means for inferential analyses were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part 1. Distribution of Mean Pretest and Posttest of the Experimental Groups

Table 1
Mean Pretest Scores of the Experimental Group 1 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge before Utilizing Interactive Learning Strategies

Vocabulary Knowledge	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Word Meaning	4.60	1.87	Good
Word Use	3.83	1.64	Fair
Context Clues	3.47	1.76	Fair

Legend: 8.00-10.00-Excellent, 6.00-7.99-Very Good, 4.00-5.99 – Good, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Poor

Table 1 presents the results of the pretest scores of the respondents who served as the experimental group 1. Based on the results, the vocabulary knowledge before using the interactive learning strategies was found to be good in word meaning with a mean of 4.60. This indicates that the students can identify and understand the meaning of the word or the definition of a specific word. They can also write simple sentences with a minimal number of vocabulary errors.

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In terms of word use, the students got a fair score with a mean of 3.83 indicating that students have fairly understood the words used in a sentence its meaning and usage. It implies that the students have knowledge about vocabulary but needs to be improved. This also suggests that students need to be given more activities regarding word use in a sentence for better understanding of the content of what they read and how they were used in a sentence (noun pronoun adjectives verb, etc.).

In the same manner, context clues test got also a fair score with a mean of 3.47 during the test indicating that the students can simply identify the meaning of the word based on how it is used in a sentence. However, some errors still can be found in the test given for context clues and word use.

Based on the students' performance in their pre-test, it is evident that the word meaning has the highest mean score which could be implied that students could simply identify the meaning of the words which can be found in the test questions. In terms of word use, it can be observed that the students' performance in their pre-test is fair. Some of the test items were easily answered by the students but they find it hard to answer most of the items in the test which means that their vocabulary knowledge must be improved.

This implies that the students should be given more exercises or activities to improve their vocabulary knowledge which is important in the mastery of four macro skills, the listening, reading, speaking and writing skills. Vocabulary is a key subject for English language students because it affects all other skills including reading, listening, writing, and speaking [3]. In connection to this, efficient teaching methods that can encourage pupils to learn actively must be sought by teachers. Aside from creating an enjoyable classroom environment, teachers must also be able to recognize that they could also develop and devise instructional materials which will fill students with positive emotion [4].

Table 2

Mean Pretest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge before Utilizing Interactive Learning Strategies

Vocabulary Knowledge	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Word Meaning	5.33	1.63	Good
Word Use	3.00	1.49	Fair
Context Clues	3.17	2.28	Fair

Legend: 8.00-10.00-Excellent, 6.00-7.99-Very Good, 4.00-5.99 – Good, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Poor

Table 2 presents the results of pretest of the respondents in experimental group 2. Based on the figures above, the students have similar results in their mean scores in the pretest given before using interactive learning strategies compared with the experimental group 1. It can be seen from the word meaning having a mean score of 5.33 which fall under the good rating. This indicates that the students can identify and understand the meaning of the word or the definition of a specific words. They can also write simple sentences with a minimal number of vocabulary errors.

Similarly, in terms of word use the students got a mean of 3.0 which falls under fair rating. This indicates that the students have fairly understood the words used in a sentence its meaning and usage. This also suggests that students need to be given more drills and exercises on the word use in a sentence for better understanding of the content of what they read and how the words will be used in a sentence, what parts of speech are they when used in a sentence or paragraph. Moreover, context clues test got also a fair score with a mean of 3.17 during the test indicating that the students can simply identify the meaning of the word on how it is used in a sentence or paragraph. However, some errors can still be found in the test given for context clues and word functions.

This implies that the students should be given more exercises or activities to improve their vocabulary knowledge which is important in the mastery of four macro skills, the listening, reading, speaking and writing skills vital to effective communication. How words are known well is described as vocabulary depth. Therefore, to be able to enhance the four macro skills in the English language, development of student's vocabulary skills should be focused in an English classroom materials which will fill students with positive emotion [5].

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Table 3
Mean Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 1 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge after Utilizing Interactive Learning Strategies

Vocabulary Knowledge	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Word Meaning	7.93	1.55	Very Good
Word Use	5.07	2.26	Good
Context Clues	6.80	2.41	Very Good

Legend: 8.00-10.00-Excellent, 6.00-7.99-Very Good, 4.00-5.99 – Good, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Poor

Results on table 3 presents the mean scores got by the students after the teacher used the interactive learning strategies to experimental group 1 using the word wizard and word connect strategies. The results are overwhelming since from good performance in word meaning it went up to a very good rating with a mean of 7.93. This implies that the students understand more the word meaning by the strategies used by the researcher. It also indicates that the students find it engaging since word wizard and word connect can be done in groups. It also makes the students think collaboratively and have a great teamwork. This is the reason why they hit the very good rating in word meaning. They can identify the meaning of the word confidently. Furthermore, less errors in the word meaning meaning identification is expected.

This result is supported by the idea that the importance of rich vocabulary knowledge in the enhancement of the language four macro skills. He also emphasized that giving the students with interactive strategies and activities, the students will be motivated to participate in the classroom, have fun and enjoy while learning [6].

In terms of word use, significant increase in the mean is very evident since from fair performance it was improved to a good rating. A mean of 5.07 manifested the crucial improvement in word use. This implies that providing interactive materials for learners that appeal to their emotion, will result to learn the second language as well as with vocabulary knowledge [7]. Thus, use of interactive strategies in teaching vocabulary develops mastery and motivation towards English language learning [8].

Lastly, the students' post test scores for the context clues resulted to a remarkable increase from fair rating to a very good rating with a mean score of 6.80 which clearly shows that the word wizard and word connect interactive learning strategies greatly helped the students to improve their vocabulary knowledge. In connection to this, similar idea that when classroom activities are enjoyable, in cognitive psychology and neuroscience standpoint, dopamine which is a neurotransmitter is released by the brain. Besides, the memory areas and acetylcholine release which also improves attentional focus. Therefore, when experiences in the classroom are engaging and pertinent to the students' lives, interests, and preferences, superior learning occurs [9].

Table 4
Mean Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge after Utilizing Interactive Learning Strategies

Vocabulary Knowledge	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Word Meaning	7.70	1.68	Very Good
Word Use	5.17	1.74	Good
Context Clues	6.53	1.91	Very Good

Legend: 8.00-10.00-Excellent, 6.00-7.99-Very Good, 4.00-5.99 – Good, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Poor

Results from table 4 presents the mean posttest scores of the respondents in the experimental group 2. It can be seen from the results that there is a significant increase in the mean scores of the respondents in terms of vocabulary knowledge. As shown on the table word meaning got a mean of 7.70 which got a very good performance. This indicates that the students have better understanding of words such as synonymous word, opposite word or even the meaning how it was used in a sentence. Lesser errors are expected for very good performance in the test and other related activities. Engaging activities such as synonyms word game and day's word activity and other strategies are effective in the development of student's vocabulary knowledge because students learn words through practice, problem solving in the completion of games, think critically and have fun and enjoy learning [10].

In word use, the students' posttest scores significantly increases since from fair performance it was improved to a good rating which can be observed from the mean of 5.17. In this case, students' performance in identifying how words are actually used

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in a sentence improved. This supported the idea that the day's word activity and synonyms word game helped students understand the words. In terms of context clues, the students' post test scores resulted to a positive increase from fair rating to a very good rating having the mean score of 6.53.

Since the activities were gamified, in oral recitation, when students were asked to use the words in a sentence, they were able to give concrete examples of sentences having used the words correctly. There are only minimal errors in terms of grammar, but the meaning of the words was correctly used. In the students' formative assessments, they got the highest marks in parts where words are used in context.

Part II. Test of Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Respondents

Table 5
Difference between Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 1 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge

Vocabulary Knowledge	Pre-test		Post Test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Word meaning	4.60	1.87	7.93	1.55	-10.947	29	0.000	Significant
Word use	3.83	1.64	5.07	2.26	-3.275	29	0.003	Significant
Context clues	3.47	1.76	6.80	2.41	-7.805	29	0.000	Significant

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

Table 5 presents the results of the mean pretest and posttest of experimental group 1. It can be seen from the figures above that in terms of vocabulary knowledge, significant difference can be found in the mean scores. T-values of -10.947, -3.275 and -7.805 with significant difference of 0.00, 0.003 and 0.00 for word meaning, word use and context clues at .05 level of significance revealed that student's performance in vocabulary knowledge has increased from fair to good rating and from good to very good rating.

In terms of word meaning, there is a significant difference between their pretest and posttest scores as the table shows that it has increased from 4.60 to 7.93. This implies that after the implementation of the study, the students improved their knowledge in terms of identifying the meaning of particular words in the test. Moreover, the students have shown enthusiasm in answering and participating in groups activities which resulted to better outputs.

Likewise, it can also be seen from the table that there is a significant difference between the students' mean pretest and posttest in terms of word use as it has increased from 3.83 to 5.07. This only suggests that students' performance in identifying the function or use of the word in a sentence has improved.

Lastly, in terms of context clues, there is also a significant difference between the students' mean pretest and posttest scores which has increased from 3.47 to 6.80. This denotes that the students were able to identify the meaning of the unfamiliar words when given relevant context or when used in a sentence. During the implementation of the strategies, the students were also able to construct simple sentences using the words which are given to them.

In conclusion, there is a statistically significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group 1 of respondents in vocabulary knowledge before and after using the interactive learning strategies such as word wizard and word connect in terms of word use, word meaning and context clues. Thus, significant improvement is very evident after using the interactive strategies in teaching English. It also indicates that exposing students to games and other interactive activities creates excellent performance in vocabulary [11].

Based on the results, the use of interactive learning strategies of different forms are effective and was supported by different studies. Furthermore, interactive strategies also improve student's spelling which found to be useful in language learning, likewise, teaching students with interactive strategies appeals to the emotions of the students that motivates them interested to learn the second language and the same goes with vocabulary [12]. Students who are actively engaged and who performed in groups improved their vocabulary knowledge. This could be supported by the idea that social constructivism is also known as collaborative learning because it is built on student involvement, discussion, and sharing. A variety of groupings and interactive techniques under the guidance of a facilitator are possible with this teaching method [13].

Table 6
 Difference between Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge

Vocabulary Knowledge	Pre-test		Post Test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Word meaning	5.33	1.63	7.70	1.68	-10.650	29	0.000	Significant
Word use	3.00	1.49	5.17	1.74	-7.629	29	0.000	Significant
Context clues	3.17	2.28	6.53	1.91	-9.427	29	0.000	Significant

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) ≤ .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) ≥ .05 (Not significant)

Table 6 presents the test of difference between the vocabulary knowledge of the experimental group 2 before and after using the interactive learning strategies. It can be gleaned from the table that in terms of word meaning a mean of 5.33 during the pretest and mean of 7.70 in the posttest revealed that a significant difference is found with a t-value of -10.650 and p-values of 0.000 at .05 level of significance which indicates that the use of interactive learning strategies greatly improves student’s vocabulary in terms of word meaning. Towards the implementation of the strategies, the students were able to recognize meanings of words as they have given the avenues and opportunities to practice identifying meanings. The results of their formative assessments revealed also that there is a retention of what they have learned.

Likewise, in terms of word use, based on the results of pretest and posttest of experimental group 2, significant difference can also be found with a t-value of -7.629 and p-values of 0.000 at .05 level of significance. Before the implementation of the strategies, students have a very limited knowledge when it comes to word use identification but after the strategies were used students improved their knowledge in analyzing what is the function of the words as used in a sentence.

Lastly, in terms of context clues, there is also a significant difference between the experimental group 2 pretest and posttest scores based on the t-value of -9.427 and p-values of 0.000 at .05 level of significance. This indicates that after synonyms and word game were used, the students improved their knowledge identifying the meaning of words based on context clues.

Based on these results, it is very apparent that the synonyms word game and day’s word activity helped the students improve their vocabulary knowledge. Since the students find the learning activities fun and enjoyable their mood lightens and they are happy, thus, learning took place. This can be supported by the idea of Krashen’s affective filter hypothesis which states that for students who are at ease and experience a welcoming learning atmosphere, more input will reach the LAD and language acquisition will be achieved. Moreover, not all of the input reaches the LAD because some of its portion is acquired however, some are filtered in this manner. The amount of input which is similarly to a gate is being filtered and controlled by the emotional filter which opens and closes depending upon what we feel. Additionally, this hypothesis of Stephen Krashen states that more input will reach the LAD and language acquisition will be achieved if we are at ease and experience a welcoming learning atmosphere. This was also supported by the the concept which explains that giving students interactive activities promote, opportunity to work independently or in group, teamwork, to become more active and collaborative in their learning experiences, and to take control of what they are learning [14].

Table 7
 Difference between Mean Pretest Scores of Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge

Vocabulary Knowledge	Experimental Group 1		Experimental Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Word meaning	4.60	1.87	5.33	1.63	-1.622	58	0.110	Not Significant
Word use	3.83	1.64	3.00	1.49	2.061	58	0.044	Significant
Context clues	3.47	1.76	3.17	2.28	0.572	58	0.570	Not Significant

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) ≤ .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) ≥ .05 (Not significant)

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Table 7 presents the results of statistical analysis of the pretest scores of experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 in vocabulary knowledge before the implementation of interactive learning strategies. It can be seen from the results, that in vocabulary knowledge, only word use found to be with significant difference. This indicates that in terms of word use or the functions of the words in a sentence, experimental group 1 performs better than to that of experimental group 2 as shown by the t-value of 2.061 and p-values of 0.044 tested at .05 level of significance. Before the implementation of the strategies, it has been already observed that experimental group 1 can identify the word use better than experimental group as it was reflected in their performance.

However, in terms of word meaning and context clues, there is no significant difference exists between the two groups of respondents. T-values of -1.622 and 0.572 respectively with p-values of 0.110 and 0.570 which is less than the alpha which is 0.05, show no difference at all. This implies that the two groups both belong to satisfactory rating in word meaning and context clues. Based on these results, it can be drawn that the vocabulary knowledge of students from experimental group 1 and group 2 in terms of word meaning and context clues are of the same level. The students from both groups are both performing good and fair in word meaning and context clues which implies that they already have understood the meaning of certain words but they need more practices and drills regarding it.

*Table 8
Difference between Mean Posttest Scores of Experimental Group 1 and
Experimental Group 2 of Respondents in Vocabulary Knowledge*

Vocabulary Knowledge	Experimental Group 1		Experimental Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Word meaning	7.93	1.55	7.70	1.68	0.56	58	0.579	Not Significant
Word use	5.07	2.26	5.17	1.74	-0.19	58	0.848	Not Significant
Context clues	6.80	2.41	6.53	1.91	0.47	58	0.637	Not Significant

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

Table 8 shows the results of the posttest mean scores of the two groups when compared. Based on the figures above, it can be found that there is no significant difference in terms of vocabulary knowledge of the two experimental groups. This is based on the results of the posttest scores taken by the respondents. It can be gleaned from the figures above that there is no significant difference exists between both groups posttest scores when compared. T-values of 0.56, -0.19, and 0.47 with p-values of 0.579, 0.848, and 0.637 respectively show beyond doubt no significant difference. Overall results are measured at 0.05 level of significance. These results show that there is no significant difference in the posttest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents because the respondents of each group increased the performance in vocabulary knowledge in terms of word meaning, word use and context clues. It only means that all the interactive learning strategies used in the experiment are effective in the development of their vocabulary knowledge as it can be seen from the pretest and posttest results of the two experimental group of respondents. Moreover, it also implies that any of those strategies used are effective and that the students participated during the activities. All of the interactive learning strategies, such as the word wizard, word connect, synonyms word game and day's word were proven to be effective. Students were highly engaged in activities which appeared to be games wherein they have to compete to make their group as the winner. Students also find it engaging and fun when learning words are treated as some sort of competition wherein they aim for good grades and rewards. Since the activities involved such as listing down words, using words in a sentence, connecting and comparing words are all fun to do, appealing and collaborative, students were learning the language or the vocabulary while they were also enjoying. Likewise, they learned more because of engaging exercises that give them fun to do it. Word connection game was used to achieve vocabulary mastery and found out that word connection game at the end of learning process had a positive impact on the experiment's group vocabulary knowledge and classroom atmosphere [15].

Based on the above results, it implies that teachers may use different strategies in teaching of any discipline but as much as possible, it should be engaging, active and fun so the students will learn while enjoying the classes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study focused in the two sections of grade 7 who served as the two experimental groups which undergone the four interactive learning strategies. Based on the results presented, it was found out that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group 1 in vocabulary knowledge in terms of word meaning, word use and context clues when tested at 0.05 level of significance. An increase in the posttest is very evident, thus, the first null hypothesis is rejected.

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In addition, there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest of the experimental group 2 in vocabulary knowledge in terms of word meaning, word use, and context clues when tested at 0.05 level of significance. A remarkable increase is very evident in the results of their posttest; thus, the second null hypothesis is rejected. There is no significant difference between mean pretest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents in vocabulary knowledge before using the interactive learning strategies in terms of word meaning and context clues when tested at 0.05 level of significance. However, when it comes to word use, there is a significant difference between their pretest scores. Thus, the third null hypothesis is partially supported or partially sustained. There is no significant difference between the posttest of the two experimental groups in vocabulary knowledge after using interactive learning strategies in terms of word meaning, word use and context clues when tested at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the results of data failed to reject the fourth null hypothesis.

Established from the summary of findings and conclusions previously discussed, several recommendations are hereby presented.. For English language teachers, since significant difference in the students' the pretest and posttest scores was found between the two experimental groups, they may consider to continuously use the different interactive learning strategies not only in vocabulary development but in the total enhancement of the four macro skills of the English language. Aside from the word connect, word wizard, syntonyms word game and day's word activity, they may also explore other interactive learning strategies to improve students' vocabulary knowledge.

For the school, it may adopt the concept of interactive learning strategies and conduct learning action cell (LAC) sessions to discuss among the teachers how to implement and utilize these strategies inside the classroom. The school may also develop Project, Programs and Activities (PPAs) which aims to enhance not only the vocabulary knowledge of the students but other macros kills as well, using this study as the basis of the PPAs. Lastly is for teachers of other discipline and future researchers, they may consider exploring and conducting studies on other various interactive strategies that will not only develop vocabulary knowledge in English but also other skills in the different disciplines in a wider scope.

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